

ISic1143

I.Sicily inscription 1143

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

found with CIL 10.7412 (ISic0183) outside the city gates of Termini in 1824

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 137

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 22.5 cm

Width 37 cm

Depth 2.3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μάξιμος

2. Διδύμου υιός

3. ἔζησεν ἔτη κγ

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation (en)

Maximos son of Didymos lived for 23 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492756

EDCS 39102300

PHI 140628

Bibliography

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